
WORK IN PROGRESS: COMMON USAGE OF ML/AI FOR RADIO ACCESS APPLICATIONS (RAN)

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ABSTRACT

Advanced technologies in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) are expected to play a critical role in the development of 6G wireless communication. However, research into the integration of AI technologies into Fifth-Generation Network (5G) networks and beyond is still in its early stages, and current research lacks comprehensive details on the process. This systematic review examines the current state of AI and ML applications in future wireless networks, with a focus on four main areas: task offloading, resource allocation, spectrum management, and channel estimation. The review identifies a range of challenges that researchers in this area face, including a lack of available data sets, limited information on tools and libraries, the impact of hardware and simulation platforms, and the need to consider the cost of implementing AI. Addressing these challenges will be key to advancing the field of AI/ML-based network research, and ongoing efforts are needed to do so.

Keywords 6G · AI · ML · Intelligent Networks

1 Introduction

The rise of 5G networks has caused an increase in the complexity and amount of demands on mobile networks [1]. However, 5G systems alone cannot offer lasting solutions to meet the growing challenges caused by massive influx of data traffic, high power consumption, and growing social demands [2]. The emergence of new use cases, such as holographic communications that require microsecond level latency [3], making it difficult for 5G networks to serve them effectively.

Moreover, it is foreseen that the classical computational methods are not able to tackle all these requirements, besides the need to innovate more modern communication technologies [4]. The challenges faced by 5G have highlighted the importance of AI and ML as a perfect complement for 5G. By learning from intricate patterns, AI/ML provides the opportunity for autonomous operations, converting 5G into a scalable, data-driven real-time network.

AI/ML applications in 5G networks are diverse and include network planning, network operation automation for optimization and security purposes, and improving both the quality of service and customer experience. In addition, AI technology is deployed to enhance performance across all network layers, beginning with the distributed cloud layer (5G Edge/Core), integrated access backhaul (IAB), and finally disaggregated radio access layer (5G RAN).

The study categorized AI applications in 5G networks and beyond into four groups based on data-driven approaches: task scheduling and offloading, resource allocation, spectrum management, and channel estimation. After categorizing research articles into these groups, the study analyzed each one based on several criteria such as the main objective in 5G Radio Access Network (RAN) application area, applied scenario, AI technique/algorithm, tools/languages used in testing and scenario realization, and the type of datasets. The most common factors considered in the reviewed articles are optimizing resources, minimizing latency, improving energy efficiency, optimizing connections, enhancing channel estimation, improving spectral efficiency, and selecting and allocating radio resources. Most of the revised articles utilized one or more AI techniques/algorithms in their proposed solutions. It is important to mention that this is preliminary work that will be further expanded in the future.

Next, the research methodology is exposed in section 2. Following, the section 3 presents a comprehensive analysis of how AI technology is currently being utilized in 5G networks. Finally, Section 4 offers conclusions and suggestions for future research in the field of AI in next-generation networks.

2 Research Methodology

To comprehensively cover the existing literature, this section outlines a systematic literature strategy to identify specific research topics. The literature survey aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the benefits derived from integrating AI mechanisms into 5G networks. It should be noted that no research has yet evaluated the cost implications of using intelligence in communication systems.

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2.1 Search Strategy

The articles were taken from the main databases, such as Scopus, IEEE Xplore, Springer Link, the ACM digital library, Wiley and MDPI. These represent current approaches, experiments, and results obtained from machine learning techniques employed in the RAN domain in 5G networks. Article search is based on various keywords and relative alternatives related to '5G RAN', 'machine learning', 'artificial intelligence' and 'deep learning', for example,

- ('5G' and 'RAN' and 'Beyond 5G') or ('AI' or 'ML')
- ('AI' or 'ML') and ('5G' or '5G RAN' or 'power consumption' or latency optimization')
- ('Deep learning' and 'energy efficiency') or ('task offloading' or 'resource allocation')
- ('ML' and 'Beyond Fifth-Generation Networks (B5G)' and 'estimation') or ('bandwidth control' or 'traffic prediction')
- ('Deep Learning (DL)' and '5G') or ('vehicular communication' or 'minimize latency')
- ('ML' and '5G') or ('Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO)' or 'millimeter Wave (mmWave)' or 'channel estimation')
- ('DL' and '5G') or ('MIMO' or 'Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM)' or 'spectrum optimization')

Due to the breadth of the field, more than 10,000 articles were initially obtained, narrowing down to 1,168 articles based on title, keywords, and publication year. After removing duplicates and non-English articles, 366 articles were left, and further screening of abstracts and introductions resulted in 189 research papers. The final phase involved reading and analyzing the full text of 112 articles, including original articles, review articles, and letters.

3 Systematic Analysis

The RAN has been crucial in connecting devices to telecommunication networks through radio links. 5G RAN technology is advanced due to its integration of innovative technology in core network architecture and air interfaces, providing fast and low-latency wireless connections. By incorporating AI/ML in 5G and beyond networks, networks can tap into the power of intelligent algorithms and software to quickly analyze data, determine how different network components interact, and manage end-to-end latency, ensuring quality of service.

RAN covers a wide range of functions and services, and this document is divided into four main categories: Task Offloading and Scheduling, Resource Allocation and Management, Spectrum Management, and Channel Estimation.

3.1 Task Offloading/Scheduling approaches ML-based

These strategies optimize offloading decisions and resource utilization, enabling end-users to achieve better service by sending computation-intensive tasks to outsourced entities such as fog nodes, mobile edge computing nodes, and cloud nodes. These entities execute tasks to ease the workload of end-users and return the results [5].

The objectives of the papers reviewed in this category are the following:

- **Resource Optimization:** Due to the limited availability of radio resources, the optimization of resources in a 5G wireless environment has become crucial, especially for Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communications (URLLC) in Machine-Type Communications (MTC). Efficient methods for optimizing resources are essential to fulfill requirements for low latency, high reliability, high density, and wide bandwidth [6].
- **Energy Efficiency:** This is a significant challenge that needs to be addressed. The primary goal is to introduce a task offloading approach that can minimize the total energy usage, while taking into account crucial factors such as sub-carriers, power, and bandwidth for offloading to ensure minimal energy consumption while fulfilling capacity and latency demands [7].
- **Minimize Latency:** The emergence of 5G wireless networks has enabled the introduction of numerous new applications and services, many of which are latency-critical, such as virtual reality, augmented reality, and vehicular communications. Task offloading is a fundamental optimization approach that minimizes latency for all users in the system by taking into account the time requirements of tasks [8].

As shown in the Figure 1, most of the reviewed papers focus on Energy Efficiency at 38%, followed by Minimize Latency at 35%, and Resource Optimization at 27% of the total task offloading section. The selected sample results indicate that Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) algorithms are the most frequently used, with rates of 30%, 34%, and 57% in Energy Efficiency, Minimize Latency, and Resource Optimization, respectively. In the Energy Efficiency subsection, Reinforcement Learning (RL) and optimization methods take second place with a ratio of 20% each. The remaining 30% is equally divided between Deep Neural Network (DNN), Supervised Learning (SL), and Neuro-fuzzy-system algorithms, each accounting for 10%. In the Minimize Latency section, DRL methods are followed by optimization methods with a ratio of 22%. Finally, the share of Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), DNN, Federated Learning (FL), and RL algorithms is equal to 11% for each. The most widely used methods in the Resource Optimization subsection are DRL, while the other methods have nearly identical rates, with 15% for FL and 14% for both RL and optimization methods.

Figure 1: AI algorithms type in Task Offloading/Scheduling

3.2 Resource Allocation and Management strategies ML-based

Efficiently managing resources in networks is a challenging task, particularly when there are vast numbers of connected users or intelligent devices. This involves effectively managing resources such as time slots, frequency bands, orthogonal codes, etc., while also considering varying traffic loads and wireless channel fluctuations. AI techniques can be leveraged to utilize past and present system knowledge, network information, user behavior, and parameters to make predictions and take control decisions to address these challenges.

The goals of the papers examined in this category are the following:

- **Resource Optimization:** Intelligent traffic prediction and monitoring methods are crucial in enhancing network performance and efficiency by considering various effective parameters of the network, especially in a dynamic network environment [9].
- **Connectivity Optimization:** This involves using machine learning algorithms to analyze data from the network, including user behavior, network traffic, and other factors, to identify patterns and make predictions about future network behavior. Based on these predictions, the AI algorithms can then optimize the network's connectivity and routing to improve performance and reduce congestion [10].
- **Energy Efficiency:** Achieving energy efficiency is one of the primary goals of resource allocation, and it can be accomplished through various techniques such as network planning and development, energy harvesting, and radio resource allocation [11].
- **Minimize Latency:** The emergence of 5G wireless networks has paved the way for numerous latency-sensitive applications and services. Resource allocation schemes are a fundamental technique utilized to reduce system latency.

The most explored categories are minimizing latency and energy efficiency with 30% each, followed by resource optimization at 24%, and connectivity optimization at 16%. Figure 2 provides an overview of the most commonly used AI algorithms, with DRL being the most prevalent method. DRL was used in 41% of energy efficiency studies and almost 35% in the other two subcategories. However, in resource optimization, DRL methods were only used in 22% of studies. RL methods were used in all subcategories except for resource optimization, with a ratio of around 12%.

Regarding NN-based algorithms, RNN methods were used in the resource optimization and connectivity optimization fields at a rate of 22% and 11%, respectively, while Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and DNN methods had a usage rate of 14% each in the resource optimization field. In the energy efficiency field, DNN and CNN occupied 12% and 6% of used algorithms, respectively, while in the minimizing latency field, RNN and CNN were used in 11% and 6% of studies, respectively.

FL methods were used in 22% of studies related to connectivity optimization, 14% in resource optimization, and 6% in minimizing latency. SL was used in the energy efficiency and minimizing latency fields at a rate of 12% and 6%, respectively. The least commonly used methods in the resource optimization category were Auto Encoder (AE) and Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP), both with an equal rate of 7%. In the minimizing latency field, Deep Belief Network (DBN) and MLP were used at a rate of 6% each.

Figure 2: AI algorithms types in Resource Allocation and Management

3.3 Spectrum Management

Managing wireless network resources is crucial due to increasing traffic demand and limited radio resources. AI, and especially DL, is a promising technology for managing interference, traffic congestion, multipathing, multi-channel access, and spectrum management in 5G networks [12]. The use of intelligent techniques can improve spectrum utilization, support the coexistence of different radio access technologies, and improve the capacity of the network [13].

The objectives of the reviewed papers in this category are:

- **Spectrum Management Optimization:** The increasing complexity of managing spectrum allocation in 5G networks calls for the development of real-time strategies to extract information and optimize spectrum access. Fine-grained spectrum optimization methods are crucial in maximizing the utilization of available spectrum resources for wireless devices [14].
- **Managing interference:** This is a critical challenge for 5G and future systems due to the ultra-dense network of small cells and coexisting numerologies within the same spectrum. To minimize interference, ML and slicing techniques are among the proposed solutions [15, 16].
- **Spectrum Efficiency:** Considered one of the Key Performance Indicator (KPI) for wireless networks, this is a fundamental metric to optimize wireless networks, since it is the relationship between data speed and bandwidth [17].
- **Energy Efficiency:** Energy conservation has gained widespread recognition as a pressing global issue in the telecommunications industry as it has serious implications for both economic and ecological costs. Emerging 5G wireless networks are expected to offer greater efficiency in the use of resources, including energy efficiency [18].

Figure 3 illustrates the distribution of AI algorithm types in the different subsections of spectrum management. The largest subsection is spectrum efficiency, accounting for 38% of the methods used, followed by spectrum management optimization with a rate of 27%, interference minimization at 22%, and energy efficiency at 13%.

In all four subsections, DRL is used, with the highest usage in energy efficiency (60%) and spectral efficiency (50%). In latency minimization, DRL accounts for 25% of the methods, while in spectrum management optimization, it is the least used at 20%.

RL algorithms have the highest usage in spectrum management optimization, with 30% of the methods used, while in energy efficiency and spectral efficiency, it is only 20% and 7%, respectively. DNN is the most widely used NN-based method, with the highest usage in interference minimization at 25%, followed by spectral efficiency and energy efficiency at 22% and 20%, respectively. RNN methods are used in minimizing interference and optimizing spectrum management at 12% and 10%, respectively.

SL algorithms are used in minimizing interference (25%) and optimizing spectrum management and spectrum efficiency at 10% and 7%, respectively. Unsupervised Learning (UL) algorithms are only used in minimizing interference (13%). FL algorithms have the highest usage in spectrum management optimization (10%) and spectral efficiency (7%). MLP and optimization methods have the lowest usage (10% each) in optimizing spectrum management, while Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) methods are only used in spectral efficiency at a rate of 7%.

3.4 Channel Estimation

In wireless communication systems, channel estimation quality has an extremely critical impact on communication performance and capacity, Since the system is directly influenced by the speed and precision of channel estimation. Achieving accurate estimation for the Channel State Information (CSI) enables maximizing network throughput. The increase in demand on the channels in 5G, creates the need for solutions using more sophisticated techniques, such as AI or ML [19]. This subsection presents the attempts of channel estimation in collaboration with AI techniques.

The main objectives of the papers reviewed in this category are:

- **Enhance Channel Estimation Accuracy:** Improve performance, robustness, and accuracy of channel estimation methods [20] [21].
- **Improve the robustness and Bit Error Rate (BER):** Manage the impact of channel estimation on the performance under different system parameters [22].
- **Improve Spectral Efficiency:** Using better channel estimation methods higher spectral efficiency can be obtained[23].

Figure 3: AI algorithms types in Spectrum Management

Considering Figure 4, the results indicated that this section is divided into three main subcategories with the following distribution: ‘enhance channel estimation accuracy’, ‘improve spectral efficiency’, and ‘improve robustness and BER’. The most dominant algorithms are Neural Network (NN)-based. Starting with ‘enhance channel estimation accuracy’, RNNs and DNNs almost share the same ratio at 22%, followed by CNNs and MLPs at 10% each. With 11% each, optimization, SL, and DRL were the other utilized methods.

Analyzing now the ‘improve spectral efficiency’ category, SL methods were the most used (29%), followed by RL (15%). The other algorithms, RNNs, DNNs, CNNs, and GANs, have similar adoption rate (14%).

The final category is ‘improve robustness and BER’, where the most used algorithms were SL-based (40%), and the NN-based algorithms formed the rest of the utilized algorithms, with DNN, CNN, and GAN being used in 20% of the papers each.

Figure 4: AI algorithms types in Channel Estimation

4 Conclusion

The research examined 112 articles in the RAN domain related to 5G and beyond networks, with results highlighting the current state of research and development on integrating AI and ML technologies into future wireless networks. In conclusion, the integration of AI and ML into 5G networks is an important area for research and development, but

there are still many challenges to address. Factors such as the lack of genuine datasets, limited information on tools and libraries, the impact of hardware and simulation platforms, and the cost of implementing AI, all hinder comparing results and validating the performance of different approaches. Future research in this field should place greater emphasis on these aspects to advance the field and facilitate collaboration between researchers and professionals.

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Appendix

Table 1: Full list of the revised papers.

Year	Ref	Network Domain	Network Operation	Area	System Model/ Topology	AI Algorithm Type
2019	[24]	HetNet Cluster	Task Offloading/ Scheduling	Resource Optimization	HetNet cluster with 3 levels, a cluster has 3-10 varied machines	RL
2019	[25]	Fog Cloud	Task Offloading/ Scheduling	Energy Efficiency	1 smart GW, 5-10 IoT MT 5 FN, 1 H-cloud server	Neuro-Fuzzy Sys. Optimization RL
2019	[26]	5G RAN	Task Offloading/ Scheduling	Energy Efficiency	1 -20 network slices/radio blocks, prediction window 3600s	DRL, RL
2019	[27]	Datacenter	Task Offloading/ Scheduling	Energy Efficiency	1 smart GW, 5-10 IoT MT 5 FN, 1 H-cloud server	DRL
2019	[28]	IoT, Edge	Task Offloading/ Scheduling	Minimize Latency	Sensing data collected by 15 IoT devices sent to 6 edge nodes for DRL training, then comparing DRL and FL	DRL, FL
2019	[29]	HUDNs	Task Offloading/ Scheduling	Minimize Latency	1 BS (a MeNB, 3 SeNBs), 20 UEs around the BS	RL

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2019	[30]	5G Cognitive Radio	Resource Allocation and Management	Resource Optimization	3 scenarios, varied network DCs capacities in 100 km^2 area, 2 M citizens	CNN
2019	[31]	5G	Resource Allocation and Management	Energy Efficiency	one BS in circle 300m radius 4 UEs, 2 REs, BW= 4 MHz	DBN
2019	[32]	Fog Vehicular	Resource Allocation and Management	Energy Efficiency	fog vehicles interact with roadside units, wireless connectivity successful transmission rate 0.9 or 0.95	RL
2019	[33]	Mobile edge computing (MEC)	Resource Allocation and Management	Minimize Latency	The Internet topology zoo [34], MEC with SDN	DRL
2019	[35]	Mobile edge computing (MEC)	Resource Allocation and Management	Minimize Latency	2 Scenarios, 1 centered edge-server in 1000 m^2 circle area, 2-12 collaborative edge servers, 10-260 MDs	DRL
2019	[36]	Vehicular Fog env.	Resource Allocation and Management	Minimize Latency	Vehicular fog computing with/without RSU, 7m between adjacent vehicles	DRL
2019	[37]	Vehicular env.	Resource Allocation and Management	Minimize Latency	Roadside units (RSUs), 100 receiver/transmitter vehicular users	FL
2019	[38]	Cognitive radio network	Spectrum Management	Spectrum Management Optimization	A railway line, trains avg speed 100ms has 10 chain-distributed cognitive BSs, each CBS has 10 primary users	RL
2019	[39]	5G Edge, Cloud env.	Spectrum Management	Minimize Interference	single-site edge cloud, multi-site IoT-cloud, 1 cloud server, 3 local servers, 15 smart devices	RNN
2019	[40]	5G, Vehicular	Spectrum Management	Minimize Interference	20 -100 vehicles, V2V links 3X number of vehicles, channel BW 1.5MHz	DRL
2019	[41]	5G RAN env.	Spectrum Management	Minimize Interference	$50 \times 40 \text{ m}$ area, 10 SC, cell density 5,000 cells $/\text{km}^2$, 1 SC connects multiple users	UL
2019	[42]	5G env., MIMO	Spectrum Management	Minimize Interference	Different scenarios for mMIMO systems	SL
2019	[43]	OFDM env.	Channel Estimation	Improve Robustness and BER	M-QAM symbol modulation, OFDM system under different multi-path fading channels	SL
2020	[44]	5G RAN	Task Offloading/Scheduling	Resource Optimization	7 cells in a hex grid layout, different scenarios over small periods, increase from 1 -100 TTI with static users	Optimization, DRL
2020	[45]	Edge Cloud	Task Offloading/Scheduling	Minimize Latency	3 edge devices, 2-8 wireless / 1-4 wired edge servers	DRL
2020	[46]	5G RAN, Vehicular	Resource Allocation and Management	Resource Optimization	many V2X communicate with RSUs where V2V and V2I are interacting	RNN, CNN, DNN
2020	[47]	Vehicular edge computing (VEC)	Resource Allocation and Management	Resource Optimization	Central server, 10 vehicles with velocity (0-15) m/s, 10 types of vehicular clients	FL, CNN
2020	[48]	Mobile edge computing (MEC)	Resource Allocation and Management	Resource Optimization	eNodeB sends info to connected MTs, 3 groups of apps	AE, MLP, RNN
2020	[49]	UDNs	Resource Allocation and Management	Resource Optimization	15 -75 UEs per UDN small cell, UDN small cell has one eNB	RNN
2020	[50]	5G RAN	Resource Allocation and Management	Resource Optimization	1 BS, 140 UEs, 5 different service types slices, scenarios considering simulation time under NSRS, RBUR, and MRB	DRL
2020	[51]	HetNet, UAV	Resource Allocation and Management	Connectivity Optimization	25 UAVs at 40m height, travel time 125s step 0.1s, find shortest path to the destination, avoid collision between UAVs	FL
2020	[52]	5G, Vehicular	Resource Allocation and Management	Connectivity Optimization	196 BS with a 40m radius, more than 50 thousand MT	RNN
2020	[53]	5G, B5G mmWave	Resource Allocation and Management	Connectivity Optimization	7 mmWave gNBs with 200 m intersite distance, waypoint mobility model generates random UE paths	DNN
2020	[54]	C-RAN	Resource Allocation and Management	Energy Efficiency	7 RRH, 7 unicast users, 7 multitask users	RNN, DRL
2020	[55]	Mobile Edge Computing, IIoT	Resource Allocation and Management	Energy Efficiency	1 BS in 500 m radius, 1 MEC, 10 - 40 IIoT devices	DRL
2020	[56]	Edge-Cloud Vehicular	Resource Allocation and Management	Energy Efficiency	100 m road, 5 roadside units 1 cloud server, VEC servers 10 vehicles	DRL
2020	[57]	F-RAN env.	Resource Allocation and Management	Minimize Latency	$400 \times 400 \text{ m}^2$, 10 fog-APs, 5 RRHs, and 30 IoT devices	DRL
2020	[58]	Vehicular Fog env.	Resource Allocation and Management	Minimize Latency	5 vehicular apps executed in FNs or cloud, data rates 10, 50, 100 Mb/s	RL
2020	[59]	Edge env.	Resource Allocation and Management	Minimize Latency	10 IoT/ 4 edge devices, 1 edge GW, 120 request/ h	DNN
2020	[60]	IoT C-RAN, MIMO	Resource Allocation and Management	Minimize Latency	$10 \times 10 \times 10 \text{ m}$ room, 128 antennas, 10 IoT devices single-antenna, BBUs linked IoTs to C-RAN	DNN
2020	[61]	Fog env.	Resource Allocation and Management	Minimize Latency	5 different configurations, 1 cloud, 1 fog node, 3 IoT sensors	SL
2020	[62]	5G RAN env.	Resource Allocation and Management	Minimize Latency	Ring network, 18 nodes, 26 links, 10 reqs at each time with 3 network slices, test samples (2k, 5k, 10k) with/without slices	CNN
2020	[63]	5G RAN env.	Spectrum Management	Spectrum Management Optimization	Choose the optimal BS for a UAV based on received signal powers, distances, and potential interference from/to the BSS	MLP

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2020	[64]	Edge env.	Spectrum Management	Spectrum Management Optimization	Area with 500m radius, 2500 devices randomly distributed, packet size 2000b	DRL
2020	[65]	Cognitive radio (CR) env.	Spectrum Management	Spectrum Management Optimization	1st-USRP-N210 with WBX USRP discone antenna, 2nd-digital spectrum analyzer Rigol DSA-875, discone antenna	RNN
2020	[66]	H-CRAN env.	Spectrum Management	Spectrum Management Optimization	Single macro cell, 500m intercell distance, 4 RRHS and vehicles light traffic- heavy traffic scenarios	RL
2020	[67]	Mobile edge computing env.	Spectrum Management	Spectrum Management Optimization	MEC network with 100m of radius, 3 BSs 6 users (uniformly distributed), task size 100- 600 kb	RL
2020	[68]	5G, RAN	Spectrum Management	Minimize Interference	The model predicting SINR, then reduces SRS ¹ transmission by half	SL
2020	[69]	5G env., MIMO	Spectrum Management	Minimize Interference	A generalized spatial Modulation MIMO system, $R_x < T_x$ antennas, QPSK values= 64, 128, 256	DNN
2020	[70]	LAA WLAN	Spectrum Management	Spectrum Efficiency	1 LTE BS has 10 UD, 1 Wi-Fi AP has 10 UD, LTE BS/Wi-Fi AP data rate 2 Mbps	RL
2020	[71]	5G RAN env. mmWave	Spectrum Management	Spectrum Efficiency	1 BS, 3 IRSs, many IRS assisted mmWave-vehicles, 1-100 users	DNN
2020	[72]	Cellular, network	Spectrum Management	Spectrum Efficiency	25 cells, half cell-to-cell distance 1 km each cell has 4 APs, located uniformly and randomly with inner space of 0.01km	DRL, DRL
2020	[73]	5G, Vehicular env.	Spectrum Management	Spectrum Efficiency	3 scenarios, 250 × 250m area, 5 BSs, 20 D2D users, 10 cellular users	DNN
2020	[74]	Ultradense IoT network	Spectrum Management	Energy Efficiency	1- 4 mmWave SBSs, each SBS serves UTs, SBSs and UTs have directional mmWave antennas	DRL
2020	[75]	5G, B5G	Spectrum Management	Energy Efficiency	DRL models with different DNN topologies distributed over SONs BS	DRL
2020	[76]	mmWave, MIMO, Vehicular env.	Channel Estimation	Enhance Channel Estimation Accuracy	MIMO mmWave, many BSs, each BS has 32 antennas serving a number of single antenna vehicular UEs	DNN, RNN
2020	[77]	5G network, mmWave, MIMO	Channel Estimation	Enhance Channel Estimation Accuracy	mMIMO mmWave, 3 BSs, BS has 256 antennas with 16 RF chains serving 16 single-antenna UEs	DNN
2020	[78]	5G network, MIMO	Channel Estimation	Improve Robustness and BER	Symbol modulation 16-QAM and 16-PSK, 2×4 MIMO with Rayleigh fading channel	DNN
2020	[79]	OFDM env.	Channel Estimation	Improve Robustness and BER	Symbol modulation 256 QAM with a single antenna OFDM, 2 statistical channel models	GAN
2020	[23]	mmWave, MIMO	Channel Estimation	Improve Spectral Efficiency	one BS has 64 R_x , 4 RF chains, 3 UT with single antenna	CNN
2021	[80]	5G RAN	Task Offloading/Scheduling	Resource Optimization	4 BSs, 40 UEs randomly distributed, 12 subcarriers, each has 15 KHz subcarrier spacing and 14 symbols per subframe	DRL
2021	[81]	IoT Edge	Task Offloading/Scheduling	Resource Optimization	3 scenarios with 6, 10, 14 tasks, between 2 and 4 edge nodes	FL, DRL
2021	[82]	Fog-RAN	Task Offloading/Scheduling	Resource Optimization	Single cell of 400 m radius 20-100 UEs, 2-10 FAPs	DRL
2021	[83]	Fog	Task Offloading/Scheduling	Energy Efficiency	Requests size 0.5 to 16 MB FN serves 50 to 100 requests	SL
2021	[84]	Edge	Task Offloading/Scheduling	Minimize Latency	50-250 devices, 10 MEC server	Optimization
2021	[85]	HetNet, UAV	Resource Allocation and Management	Resource Optimization	2 scenarios, 5 UAVs/3 subareas, 7 UAVs/6 subareas, final matching based on returned reward and marginal costs	FL
2021	[86]	5G, B5G	Resource Allocation and Management	Resource Optimization	Two scenarios, 7 C-RAN nodes, 17 NG-RAN nodes	DRL
2021	[87]	5G, Vehicular	Resource Allocation and Management	Connectivity Optimization	Edge cluster has 7 FN, 10 utility values of IoV and smart city apps	DRL
2021	[88]	5G RAN mmWave	Resource Allocation and Management	Connectivity Optimization	2 UEs using 16QAM, 4 flows, testing SINR per (0 to 800) subcarrier in different scenarios	DRL
2021	[89]	HetNet UAV, Vehicular	Resource Allocation and Management	Connectivity Optimization	3 cells, 6 UAVs, allocation UAVs to cells after analyzing the preference and efficiency in the UAV-enabled network	FL
2021	[90]	HetNet, mmWave	Resource Allocation and Management	Connectivity Optimization	3 scenarios, macro BS serving at 3GHz has small cells at 28 GHz	RL
2021	[91]	5G	Resource Allocation and Management	Connectivity Optimization	3 BSs, 2 network slices each NS has < 8 users	DRL
2021	[92]	6G	Resource Allocation and Management	Connectivity Optimization	IoT-Cloud-SDN/NFV enviro., smartX MicroBoxes forming edge clusters	RNN
2021	[93]	F-RAN	Resource Allocation and Management	Energy Efficiency	Fog-RAN network, 1 MBS radius 500m, 20 fog-AP change randomly in MBS, 200 Fog-UEs randomly distributed	Optimization
2021	[94]	Edge, RAN	Resource Allocation and Management	Energy Efficiency	7 BSs have 21 sectors, 10 UEs per sector	RNN

2021	[95]	MEC	Resource Allocation and Management	Energy Efficiency	MEC environment, 1 BS, 1 MEC server, 2-30 users	DRL
2021	[96]	5G, MIMO	Resource Allocation and Management	Energy Efficiency	mMIMO BS (16X8), 40 UE, 7 UE moving with a speed of 1.5m/s	RL
2021	[97]	Mobile Edge Computing, IoT	Resource Allocation and Management	Energy Efficiency	$100 \times 100 m^2$ 2D area, 1 MEC server multiple UEs, random sensor positions	DRL
2021	[98]	Wifi network environment	Resource Allocation and Management	Energy Efficiency	APs with different user activities, (RMSE, MAE, R2, Var) performance metrics, in (15, 30, 45, 60 minutes)	CNN
2021	[99]	5G, IoT env.	Resource Allocation and Management	Minimize Latency	10 resource servers, 30 -120 IoT devices, 20 - 200 requests	DNN
2021	[100]	HetNet env.	Resource Allocation and Management	Minimize Latency	Network traffic is classified into 3 classes high, medium, and low priority	SL
2021	[101]	HetNet, V-RAN env.	Resource Allocation and Management	Minimize Latency	1 Edge Host, 2 MTs, each MT linked to 2 USRP B210 boards that implement LTE and IEEE 802.11p	RL
2021	[102]	5G, Vehicular env.	Spectrum Management	Spectrum Management Optimization	$125 \times 216m$ area, vehicle speed 36 km/s, 4 V2I links, 4 V2V links, BW 4MHz	DRL
2022	[103]	Indoor 5G	Spectrum Management	Spectrum Management Optimization	Comparing time to compute network deployment and coverage rate, for required APs under different criteria	SL, Optimization
2021	[104]	Fly BS, B5G env.	Spectrum Management	Minimize Interference	Simulation area with 1 km x 1 km, 400 users, scenarios considering (3 to 24) Flying base stations (FlyBSs)	DNN
2021	[105]	5G RAN, 6G network	Spectrum Management	Spectrum Efficiency	1 slice (uRLLC) higher weighting factor, 1 slice (eMBB), 50 RB, BW 180kHz	DRL, DRL
2021	[106]	Industrial IoT env.	Spectrum Management	Spectrum Efficiency	10 Industrial gateways, each equipped with a Raspberry Pi 4B, connected with 35 IIoT devices	DRL
2021	[107]	5G, IoT env.	Spectrum Management	Spectrum Efficiency	Different numbers of IoT devices in the range of 15 to 150	SL
2021	[108]	5G env., UAV	Spectrum Management	Spectrum Efficiency	Different symbol modulation schemes, Rayleigh channel	DNN
2021	[109]	5G RAN	Spectrum Management	Energy Efficiency	10 slices split into 4 resource-based, 6 rate-based, 200 RAN RB, RB BW 1.8KHz	DRL
2021	[110]	5G RAN	Channel Estimation	Enhance Channel Estimation Accuracy	Cell radius 500m, 1st slice with 30 UEs 2nd slice with 70 UEs, and SNR varies from -10 dB to 5 dB	RNN, CNN DRL
2021	[111]	B5G env., MIMO	Channel Estimation	Enhance Channel Estimation Accuracy	Symbol modulation QPSK with OFDM, downlink system with 32×4 MIMO mmWave channel	MLP
2021	[112]	mmWave env.	Channel Estimation	Enhance Channel Estimation Accuracy	Symbol modulation 16QAM, OFDM mmWave-based system	SL
2021	[113]	IoT env.	Channel Estimation	Enhance Channel Estimation Accuracy	An uplink system, BS has 40-60 receive antennas serve 1000 single antenna-IoT devices, 80 of them are active	Optimization
2021	[114]	mMIMO, OFDM env.	Channel Estimation	Improve Robustness and BER	OFDM mMIMO, symbol modulation QPSK and 16QAM, BS has multiple antennas and serves many single-antenna UEs	SL
2021	[115]	5G network, OFDM	Channel Estimation	Improve Spectral Efficiency	3 scenarios, symbol modulation QPSK, SISO OFDM system, slow fading channel	SL
2021	[116]	5G network, OFDM	Channel Estimation	Improve Spectral Efficiency	one BS, downlink multi-user SISO OFDM-NOMA based system under Rayleigh fading channel	RNN
2021	[117]	B5G env., MIMO	Channel Estimation	Improve Spectral Efficiency	mmWave MIMO AP has 36 transmit antennas serving single antenna UE	CNN
2022	[118]	5G, 6G	Spectrum Management	Energy Efficiency	Wi-Fi direct scenario, 255 Max D2D, Max D2D distance is 200m, LTE direct scenario, 2000 Max D2D, D2D distance is 600m UE can connect to a D2D network or BS	RL DNN
2022	[119]	5G SON , network	Spectrum Management	Minimize Interference	Inter-Site distance 0.5-2 Km, BW 5MHz, 45 eNBs, 120 edge sector, 600 mobile	DRL
2022	[120]	mmWave, MIMO env.	Spectrum Management	Spectrum Efficiency	Single user mMIMO systems, antennas, (64/256)Tx antennas, 4 RF chains, multiple data stream	DRL
2022	[121]	Mobile Edge Computing	Task Offloading/ Scheduling	Energy Efficiency	500 tasks offloaded into MT, SBS, and main BS (MBS)	Optimization
2022	[122]	MEC	Task Offloading/ Scheduling	Energy Efficiency	1 BS, 8 SBS, 30 ENs Max 40 UE per BS	DRL
2022	[123]	Software-Defined Industrial Fog net.	Task Offloading/ Scheduling	Energy Efficiency	1 SC, 5-10 UE, 4 FN Task size 2-20 MB	DRL
2022	[124]	IoT Fog	Task Offloading/ Scheduling	Minimize Latency	500 tasks, 5 edge servers 50 terminal devices	DRL, RNN
2022	[125]	IoT Fog	Task Offloading/ Scheduling	Minimize Latency	150 tasks, 200 Fog servers	CNN, Optimization
2022	[126]	Industrial wireless networks (IWNs)	Resource Allocation and Management	Energy Efficiency	3 Industrial BS with 1 km radius, 10-55 MTDs, BW = 10 MHz	DRL

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2022	[127]	IoT, Edge Cloud	Resource Allocation and Management	Energy Efficiency	Cloud node, 2 fog nodes, 1 GW	MLP
2022	[128]	5G RAN	Resource Allocation and Management	Energy Efficiency	2 microcell BS, one BS mostly active one BS is active only in public events	SL
2022	[129]	Mobile IoT	Resource Allocation and Management	Energy Efficiency	Implement a transmit antenna selection (TAS)-based secrecy scheme employing amplify-and-forward (AF) relaying	Optimization
2022	[130]	Mobile edge computing, Cloud	Resource Allocation and Management	Minimize Latency	MEC 520x520m area, 5 BSs MEC 10-55, UT 20-80	DRL
2022	[131]	Mobile edge computing env.	Resource Allocation and Management	Minimize Latency	Users 10 - 110	DRL
2022	[132]	HetNet FRAN env.	Resource Allocation and Management	Minimize Latency	A layered FRAN environment (MCs, SBSs, MBSs, and a cloud), with cache size varies from 0.1% to 1%.	DRL
2022	[133]	5G network	Spectrum Management	Spectrum Efficiency	Two modulation schemes, AWGN channel, receiver SNR range from -20 to 10dB	GAN
2022	[134]	5G network	Channel Estimation	Improve Robustness and BER	Considering BER as a performance metric under nonidentical fading channels	CNN
2022	[135]	5G network, MIMO	Channel Estimation	Improve Spectral Efficiency	7 cells, each has 1 BS equipped with 256 antennas serving single-antenna users, 10 UEs (4 user per cell)	RL

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